

Chemical Constituents of *Carissa spinarum* and their Antibacterial Activity

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Carissa spinarum L. (Apocynaceae) is known as *Karamadika* in Sanskrit and *Chirukala* in Tamil. Its medicinal uses are described in the traditional system of medicine. The roots are purgative and the root powder is applied to the worm-infested sores of animals¹. The leaves are reported to possess cardiotoxic, diuretic and hypotensive properties². Literature survey shows that there is no report on the chemical constituents of this plant. In this communication we report the isolation and characterization of ursolic acid (**1**) and naringin (**2**) from the leaves and their antibacterial activity.

Hexane and chloroform extracts on chromatography over silica gel yielded a triterpenoid acid, C₃₀H₄₈O₃, m.p. 282–84°. It formed a monoacetate, m.p. 284–85°, with pyridine and acetic anhydride. Comparison of ¹H and ¹³C nmr data of the compound and its monoacetate with those of pentacyclic triterpenoid acids established its identity as ursolic acid (**1**).

n-BuOH soluble portion of the methanol extract on chro-

matography over silica gel afforded a pale yellow solid as an amorphous hygroscopic powder (**2**), C₂₇H₃₂O₁₄. It responded to Shinoda test and tests for phenol and sugar, indicating it to be a flavonoid glycoside. Its uv spectrum showed an inflection of low intensity at 327 nm (Band I) and a strong absorption at 280 nm (Band II) as expected for a flavanone. The ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra of **2** were consistent with the presence of a 4',5,7-trioxygenated flavone and two sugar units. On acid hydrolysis **2** indeed gave L-rhamnose and D-glucose and an aglycone, m.p. 249–50°. Acetylation of **2** with NaOAc and Ac₂O gave an octaacetate (**3**). The presence of α-L-rhamnosyl (1 → 2)-β-D-glucopyranosyl unit and its attachment with C-7 oxygen function of flavanone were secured from extensive high resolution nmr experiments such as ¹H nmr, ¹³C nmr, homodecoupling and ¹H-¹H nmr correlation studies on **3**. The ¹³C shifts observed for **2** in CD₃OD at room temperature were fairly similar to those reported for naringin³ in DMSO-d₆ at 95°. The aglycone was subsequently identified as naringenin. This is the first report of isolation of ursolic acid and naringin from this plant.

The methanol extract of the leaves of *C. spinarum* and its isolates ursolic acid and naringin in agar dilution streak method completely inhibited the pathogenic Gram-negative bacteria which cause diarrhoea and dysentery. The results of *in vitro* antibacterial activity studies using tube dilution method (MIC) are given in Table 1. All of them were able to inhibit the pathogenic organisms even at a concentration of less than 1 mg except *E. coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Naringin and ursolic acid had similar antibacterial activities.

TABLE 1—MINIMUM INHIBITORY CONCENTRATION (mg ml⁻¹)*

Extract/ isolate	<i>S.s</i>	<i>S.b</i>	<i>S.f</i>	<i>V.c</i>	<i>E.c</i>	<i>K.p</i>
Methanol extract	0.832	0.832	0.832	0.416	0.832	0.416
Ursolic acid	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0
Naringin	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0

**S.s* = *Shigella sonnei*, *S.b* = *S. boydii*, *S.f* = *S. flexneri*, *V.c* = *V. cholerae*, *E.c* = *E. coli*, *K.p* = *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

Experimental

^1H nmr spectra were recorded on a Bruker AM 300 L Supercon spectrometer at 300.13 MHz relative to TMS and ^{13}C nmr spectra were run at 75.5 MHz. Standard procedures were used for nmr experiments. The leaves of *C. spinarum* were collected from Vanamadevi of South Arcot Vallalar District, Tamil Nadu. The identity of the plant was confirmed at Madras Herbarium, Botanical Survey of India, Coimbatore (M.H. 56059).

Isolation of ursolic acid (1): Coarsely powdered air-dried leaves (2 kg) were extracted with n-hexane, CHCl_3 and MeOH successively in the cold. Hexane and CHCl_3 extracts were combined and subjected to column chromatography on silica gel. CHCl_3 eluates on purification by rechromatography over silica gel yielded a colourless solid **1** (500 mg), m.p. 282–84°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3500–3400, 1690, 1650, 1450, 1385, 1030 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (CDCl_3 – CD_3OD) δ 0.78, 0.82, 0.93, 0.99, 1.10 (3H each, s each, $5 \times \text{CH}_3$), 0.87 (3H, d, J 6.4 Hz, CH_3), 0.97 (3H, d, J 6.8 Hz, CH_3), 2.2 (1H, d, J 11.2 Hz, H-18), 3.20 (1H, dd, J 7.8 and 8.1 Hz, H-3), 5.24 (1H, t, J 3.4 Hz, H-12); ^{13}C nmr (CDCl_3 – CD_3OD) δ 38.4 (C-1), 26.5 (C-2), 78.5 (C-3), 38.5 (C-4), 55.1 (C-5), 18.0 (C-6), 32.8 (C-7), 39.3 (C-8), 47.4 (C-9), 36.7 (C-10), 23.0 (C-11), 125.3 (C-12), 138.0 (C-13), 41.8 (C-14), 27.8 (C-15), 23.9 (C-16), 47.6 (C-17), 52.7 (C-18), 38.8 (C-19), 38.7 (C-20), 30.4 (C-21), 36.5 (C-22), 27.6 (C-23), 14.9 (C-24), 15.1 (C-25), 16.5 (C-26), 23.1 (C-27), 180.2 (C-28), 16.5 (C-29), 20.6 (C-30).

Acetylation of 1: Compound **1** (100 mg) in dry pyridine (1 ml) was treated with Ac_2O (2 ml) and the mixture kept at room temperature overnight. Work-up in the usual way gave the monoacetate which was crystallized from methanol (80 mg), m.p. 284–85°; ^1H nmr (CDCl_3) δ 0.76, 0.85, 1.07 (3H each, s each, $3 \times \text{CH}_3$), 0.96 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 0.86 (6H, d, J 5.6 Hz, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 2.05 (3H, s, $1 \times \text{OAc}$), 2.18 (1H, d, J 11.1 Hz, H-18), 4.5 (1H, dd, J 7.5 and 8.1 Hz, H-3), 5.23 (1H, br s, H-12); ^{13}C nmr (CDCl_3) δ 38.2 (C-1), 23.2 (C-2), 80.9 (C-3), 37.7 (C-4), 55.2 (C-5), 18.1 (C-6), 32.8 (C-7), 39.4 (C-8), 47.4 (C-9), 36.9 (C-10), 23.6 (C-11), 125.7 (C-12), 137.9 (C-13), 41.8 (C-14), 27.9 (C-15), 24.0 (C-16), 47.9 (C-17), 52.4 (C-18), 39.0 (C-19), 38.8 (C-20), 30.6 (C-21), 36.7 (C-22), 27.9 (C-23), 17.1 (C-24), 15.5 (C-25), 16.7 (C-26), 23.6 (C-27), 184.2 (C-28), 17.0 (C-29), 21.2 (C-30), 171.0 (OCOCH_3), 21.3 (OCOCH_3).

Isolation of naringin (2): Methanol extract on concentration yielded more of **1** (2 g). The mother liquor was extracted with n-butanol and the butanol extract was chromatographed through a column of silica gel. EtOAc–MeOH (9 : 1) eluates afforded a gum which was purified by

rechromatography over silica gel to give a pale yellow solid as an amorphous hygroscopic powder **2** (1.2 g); ν_{max} (KBr) 3400, 2900, 1640, 1610, 1370, 1200 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 209, 230 (sh), 280, 327 nm; ^1H nmr (CD_3OD) δ 1.23 (3H, d, J 6.3 Hz, H_3 -6'''), 2.66 (1H, br d, J 17.1 Hz, H_a -3), 3.06 (1H, dd, J 12.9 and 17.1 Hz, H_b -3), 3.15–4.05 (10H, complex), 5.01 (1H, d, J 6.9 Hz, H-1''), 5.19 (1H, br s, H-1'''), 5.27 (1H, br d, J 12.9 Hz, H-2), 6.76 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, H-3', 5') and 7.27 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, H-2', 6'); ^{13}C nmr (CD_3OD) δ 80.5 (C-2), 44.0 (C-3), 198.4 (C-4), 164.8 (C-5), 98.0 (C-6), 166.6 (C-7), 96.9 (C-8), 164.5 (C-9), 105.0 (C-10), 130.8 (C-1'), 129.0 (C-2', 6'), 116.5 (C-3', 5'), 158.9 (C-4'), 99.6 (C-1''), 79.2 (C-2''), 78.8 (C-3''), 72.3 (C-4''), 78.0 (C-5''), 62.4 (C-6''), 102.4 (C-1'''), 72.1 (C-2'''), 71.4 (C-3'''), 74.0 (C-4'''), 70.0 (C-5''') and 18.1 ppm (C-6''').

Acetylation of 2: Compound **2** (150 mg) was refluxed with twice its weight of freshly fused NaOAc and Ac_2O (3 ml) in an oil-bath for 4 h. The mixture was worked up in the usual way and purified by chromatography over silica gel. C_6H_6 – CHCl_3 (9 : 1) eluates yielded the octaacetate **3** (120 mg), m.p. 138–40°; ^1H nmr (CDCl_3) δ 1.20 (3H, d, J 6.2 Hz, H-6'''), 1.96, 1.97, 1.973, 2.02, 2.09, 2.12 (3H each, s each, $6 \times \text{OAc}$), 2.30, 2.36 (3H each, s each, $2 \times$ phenolic OAc), 2.73 (1H, dd, J 2.9 and 16.8 Hz, H_b -3), 3.01 (1H, dd, J 13.4 and 16.8 Hz, H_a -3), 3.87 (1H, m, H-5''), 3.97 (1H, dd, J 9.1 and 7.7 Hz, H-2''), 4.04 (1H, dq, J 9.5 and 6.3 Hz, H-5'''), 4.12 (1H, dd, J 2.4 and 12.3 Hz, H_a -6''), 4.2 (1H, dd, J 5.9 and 12.3 Hz, H_b -6''), 4.999 (1H, t, J 9.7 Hz, H-4''), 5.0 (br s, H-1''' and H-2''' signals merged), 5.04 (1H, t, J 9.8 Hz, H-4'''), 5.11 (1H, d, J 7.7 Hz, H-1''), 5.15 (1H, dd, J 2.8 and 9.9 Hz, H-3'''), 5.32 (1H, t, J 9.3 Hz, H-3''), 5.45 (1H, dd, J 2.4 and 13.4 Hz, H-2), 6.34 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz, H-6), 6.55 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz, H-8), 7.14 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-3' and 5'), 7.44 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-2' and 6'); ^{13}C nmr (CDCl_3) δ 79.3 (C-2), 45.1 (C-3), 188.3 (C-4), 152.1 (C-5), 106.2 (C-6), 163.9 (C-7), 102.6 (C-8), 162.0 (C-9), 109.9 (C-10), 135.7 (C-1'), 127.3 (C-2', 6'), 122.0 (C-3', 5'), 151.2 (C-4'), 98.3 (C-1''), 76.9 (C-2''), 74.2 (C-3''), 68.7 (C-4''), 72.6 (C-5''), 62.1 (C-6''), 98.7 (C-1'''), 70.2 (C-2'''), 68.7 (C-3'''), 71.1 (C-4'''), 67.1 (C-5'''), 17.5 (C-6'''), 168.9, 169.5, 169.9, 170.2 (acetate CO), 20.5, 20.7 and 20.9 ppm (acetate Me).

Antibacterial activity: Agar dilution streak method was used for the qualitative evaluation of antibacterial activity⁴. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of plant extract and its isolates **1** and **2** was estimated using tube dilution method⁵. MeOH extract as well as **1** and **2** were dissolved in 2% DMSO to give a concentration of 10 mg ml^{-1} .

In the agar dilution streak method, the samples (10 ml) were introduced aseptically into presterilized petri dishes. Nutrient agar was prepared and before congealing 10 ml of the agar medium was added to each of the petri plates containing the samples and the petri plates were swirled until the agar began to set. The organisms were streaked readily on the agar and the plates were incubated at 37° for 24 h.

In the tube dilution method, equal volumes of nutrient broth were taken up in six tubes. Same volume of the sample was added to the first tube and therein decreasing dilutions were prepared (1 : 2, 1 : 4, 1 : 8, 1 : 16, 1 : 32). A sample control and a solvent control (2% DMSO) were also maintained. Finally same volumes of a 24 h culture (10^6 cfu/ml) were added to all the tubes and then incubated at 37° for 24 h. Next day a loopful of the mixture was streaked on to a fresh nutrient agar plate to find out the minimum lethal concentration.

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